

**SCIENCE AND EDUCATION
IN KARAKALPAKSTAN**

**ҚОРАҚАЛПОҒИСТОНДА
ФАН ВА ТАЪЛИМ**

**ҚАРАҚАЛПАҚСТАНДА
ИЛИМ ҲЭМ ТЭЛИМ**

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THE VALUE OF DECORATIVE TREES IN THE ECOSYSTEM OF THE CITY

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Summary: *The article describes the current state of plants and trees in the ecosystem of Samarkand, and studies the ongoing reforms in their conservation. At the end of the article it is recommended to pay special attention to three tasks in the conservation of flora in the ecosystem of Samarkand.*

Key words: *city, gardens, trees, medicinal plants.*

Samarkand is one of the oldest cities in the world, rich not only in ancient, historical and architectural monuments, but also in the wonderful flora. In his memoirs, Rui Gonzalez de Clavejo, a Spanish traveler, described Samarkand as "the whole city is surrounded by gardens and vineyards." [1]. We know that many of the trees mentioned in the pages of history have died out over time for various reasons, some of which have not yet survived. It should be noted that landscaping of Samarkand on the basis of a special plan has not been stopped. After all, the city of Samarkand preserving the uniqueness of the century is an important task of every era. The urgency of the topic is demonstrated by the need to realize the uniqueness of the urban ecosystem not only by preserving historical monuments, building multi-storey, modern buildings, but also by studying, preserving and enriching the rich nature, plants and trees. After all, we have a rich nature with plants and rare trees that attract foreign tourists.

Natural monuments in the ecosystem of Samarkand, in particular, Two-piece ginkgo (*Ginkgo biloba*), Swamp cypress (*Taxodium distichum*), Virginia spruce, juniper (*Juniperus virginiana* L.), Giant sequoiadendron, mammoth tree (*Sequoiadendron givante*), Crimean pine, Pallas pine (*Pinus pallasiana*), Birch, iron tree (*Celtis caucasica*), Canadian birch, button tree (*Gymnocladus dioica*), Fake chestnut, horse chestnut (*Aesculus hippocastanum*), Heartberry linden, Tilia Rare trees such as blackberry (*Fraxinus pensylvanica*), evergreen sesame (*Buxus sempervireng*), Japanese sophora, eggplant (*Sophora japonica*), Oriental maple (*Platanus orientalis*), brown oak (*Quercus robur*) are also of great importance. rare trees are giving the city an aesthetic beauty. Unfortunately, over the years, the destruction of many rare trees and shrubs in Samarkand has further strengthened the artificiality of the city's ecosystem. We must not forget that the diversity and abundance of trees and plants in the city is a "source of life" for the population.

Samarkand Fairy Tale is also of great importance in the flora of Samarkand. It is an early-ripening apple variety in Samarkand. This tree, whose fruits are small, thin and sweet, is recommended for planting in urban gardens [3].

In the management of ecosystems in our country, great attention is paid to the preservation of plants and special legal measures are taken. We can see this clearly in the legal measures that are being taken. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the activities of the State Service for Plant Quarantine" (No. PP-4861), "Protection of wild-growing medicinal plants, cultural cultivation, Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4670 of April 10, 2020 "On measures for the processing and rational use of available resources", Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-409 of September 21, 2016 "On protection and use of flora" [4] The new version of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a clear example of this.

In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4670 "On the protection, cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of wild-growing medicinal plants.

According to the resolution of April 10, 2020 "On measures for the use of medicinal plants in our country, there is a need to protect medicinal plants." The resolution notes that 750 species of

more than 4.3 thousand plants belonging to the local flora are medicinal, of which 112 species are registered for use in scientific medicine, of which 70 species are actively used in the pharmaceutical industry. The appendix to the resolution contains a list of areas specializing in the cultivation of the main types of medicinal plants, and Samarkand is included in the list of areas specializing in the cultivation of the main types of medicinal plants. Also in Samarkand are Bitter Almond (*Amygdalus bucharica* Korsh.), Bitter Pepper (*Capsicum annum*L.), Bitter Ermon (*Artemisia absinthium* L.), Medicinal Dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale* FHWIGG.), Medicinal Chamomile (*Matricargul*). (*Calendula officinalis*L.), Pear (Topinambup) (*Helianthus tuberosus* L.), Jumrutsimon chakanda (*Hippopha rhamnoides* L.), Iturun na'matagi (*Rosa canina* L.), Maydagulli tograykhon - (*Origanum thiythanthum* Gontschbo.), Tandi. vulgare L.), common fennel (*Pimpinella anisum*L.), Samarkand alfalfa (*Helichrysum maracandicum* Popov ex Kirp.), perforated field, coarse-grained field (*Hypericum perforatum* L.) (*Hupericum skabrum* L.), Turkestan hawthorn (*Crata hawthorn*).) is recommended for planting medicinal plants such as

Within the framework of the program "Every family is an entrepreneur", each family living in Samarkand can grow some of the above medicinal plants (common fennel, hot pepper, thyme, chamomile, medicinal thyme) at home. In this way, they can not only meet their own needs, but also meet the needs of the domestic market and make a financial profit by exporting them.

In particular, the common fennel (*Pimpinella anisum*L.), Which is distinguished among medicinal plants by its aroma, is used in medicine to give the drug a fragrant taste, is a medicinal plant with expectorant and intestinal function [5]. This plant is also grown in Samarkand. It is mainly used by the population for urination and weeding.

Rosehip tincture is another medicinal plant used in the treatment of uterine diseases, gastrointestinal and gynecological diseases Medicinal chamomile (*Matricaria recutita* L.) [5], [6], which can also be grown in private gardens in the city. Another importance of this medicinal plant is that it can be consumed as a gargle or herbal tea when the respiratory tract is inflamed. This plant is also grown as a medicinal plant in homes in Samarkand.

Bitter pepper (*Capsicum annum*L.) Is also a medicinal plant grown in homes in Samarkand. This plant is a cure for many diseases (arthritis, rheumatism, radiculitis, etc.) and contains many vitamins C, R, V2 and the like.

Another common medicinal plant throughout Samarkand is the capsella bursa-pastoris (L.) Medic [5]. Rich in glycosides, vitamins, ascorbic acid and many other vitamins, this medicinal plant is used by the population to prepare and consume many delicious dishes. It is used to stop bleeding from the uterus after childbirth from drugs made from the medicinal plant of the jaw.

Another medicinal plant rich in fragrant, urban ecosystems, rich in vitamins, is Maydagulli toraigoni (*Origanum thiythanthum* Gontsch.) [5], [6]. This medicinal plant, which has an analgesic effect and is an important antimicrobial agent in inflammation, grows mainly in the open meadows and rocky soils of Samarkand. However, even within the city, it is possible to grow this perennial medicinal plant. At present, every household in Samarkand grows *Ocimum basilicum* L., which contains essential oil and camphor [5]. This plant can be found in the squares in front of high-rise buildings, in the alleys, in particular, on the territory of the Samarkand State Institute of Architecture and Construction.

Of course, we must also realize that the natural environment is based on the creation of home gardens, in which we can grow many plants, along with fruit trees, as well as medicinal plants. After all, in order to restore health and fight the disease in a pandemic, it is advisable for city residents to grow medicinal plants at home.

Given the presence of aquatic plants in the ecosystem of Samarkand, including forage, medicinal and decorative species, as well as plant species used as building materials, their study is of great scientific and practical importance, and some of them require special measures for their protection. need to be developed [7]. Aquatic plants are also part of the ecosystem.

Due to the high emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere in the city, it is necessary to increase the natural environment in Samarkand by reducing the artificial environment. The artificial

environment can be somewhat restricted in exchange for the formation of a natural environment such as a garden, small forests [8].

In conclusion, it can be said that every city in our country is as unique as Samarkand. Based on the study of plants and trees in Samarkand, we identified a number of important tasks. We will consider them below:

First, legal measures are not the only measure in the preservation of plants in our city. Unauthorized felling of trees on the streets is also common in our country. It is also necessary to increase the activity of the population on the basis of supporting their love for plants and creating opportunities.

Second, the population should be regularly informed about rare trees and medicinal plants. Of course, this can be said to be done on the basis of special shows on TV, but it would have been more effective if experts had gone to the neighborhoods and accelerated the explanatory work. In this way, we would have prepared the population a little for any pandemic conditions.

Third, it is necessary to conduct sociological surveys on the topic "Flora of Samarkand" or "Natural monuments of Samarkand" and expand similar sociological surveys among the population. In this way, it is possible to identify the latent attitude of the population towards plants and develop a program of action when it is negative.

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Rezyume: *Maqolada Samarqand shahri ekotizimidagi o'simliklar va daraxtlarning joriy holati yoritilgan bo'lib, ularni asrab avaylashda amalga oshirilgan islohotlar o'rganilgan. Moqala so'ngida Samarqand shahri ekotizimidagi o'simliklar dunyosini asrab avaylashda uchta vazifaga alohida e'tibor berish lozimligi tavsifa etilgan.*

Резюме: *В статье описывается современное состояние растений и деревьев в экосистеме города Самарканда и реформы по их сохранению. В конце статьи рекомендуется обратить особое внимание на три задачи по сохранению растительного мира в экосистеме города Самарканда*

Kalit so'zlar: *shahar, bog'lar, daraxtlar, dorivor o'simliklar.*

Ключевые слова: *Город, сады, деревья, лекарственные растения.*